

INFRARED ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES AND CARBIDE FORMATION

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ABSTRACT

Aluminum matrix composites with carbon fiber, Nicalon fiber and SCS-2 reinforcements have been fabricated with an innovative infrared infiltration technique. With infrared infiltration, no vacuum or external pressure were required. Composites were typically made within 1-2 minutes. Composites made with infrared show excellent wetting between the matrix and the reinforcements. The longitudinal strength measured with the bend test is up to 722 MPa for the 12 vol% SCS-2 fiber reinforced 6061 Al composite. Due to rapid infrared heating, the interfacial reaction in the composites is limited. Carbide was observed in the as fabricated composites. The formation of carbide at the interface was discussed. TEM was used to reveal the growth of carbide from the fiber surface.

INTRODUCTION

Aluminum matrix composites have been fabricated by several different techniques. Among these are solid state diffusion bonding, semi-liquid state hot pressing, liquid state pressure infiltration and liquid state vacuum infiltration [1]. Compared to solid state processes, liquid state processing have many advantages such as low cost and the ability to process composites of intricate shapes with high volume fractions of reinforcements. The most common liquid infiltration technology uses external pressures, either by mechanical means or inert gases, to infiltrate pre-evacuated preforms[2-4]. Due to the requirement of vacuum operation at high temperatures and pressures, liquid infiltration is still considered a high cost process. It is obvious that if the requirement of pressure and vacuum can be eliminated, the cost of processing can be further reduced.

There have been a few attempts to fabricate aluminum matrix composites without the application of vacuum or external pressure. Rocher et al. [5] coated the fibers with potassium hexafluoro-zirconate (K_2ZrF_6), a flux used in the light metal foundry to facilitate wetting to assist infiltration. They were successful in producing a 10 vol% Nicalon fiber reinforced Al-7Si-0.6Mg alloy composite without the application of pressure or vacuum by conventional casting techniques. The strength of these composites were about 60% higher than that of the unreinforced alloy. The strength of the fibers after the infiltration was reduced by about 30%. No further information on the properties of composites fabricated by liquid infiltration with the K_2ZrF_6 treatment was

reported. In a subsequent study, Rocher et al. [6] examined the effect of K_2ZrF_6 on the wettability of aluminum on carbon and SiC substrates in a vacuum of 10^{-4} to 5×10^{-4} Pa. In their study, a large amount of the flux per unit fiber surface area ($> 5 \text{ mg/cm}^2$) was required even under vacuum to produce acceptable wetting behavior during infiltration. Unfortunately, due to the excess amount of flux used, high fiber volume fraction composites can not be produced by this process. Furthermore, substantial amounts of reaction products such as Al_3Zr exist in the composite as a result of large amounts of the flux used. This can be detrimental to the mechanical properties of the composite.

In a different attempt, Lanxide Corporation [7-9] uses a liquid infiltration process to fabricate aluminum matrix composites without vacuum or external pressure. The process is based on the effect of spontaneous wetting of ceramics by molten aluminum alloys containing magnesium in a nitrogen atmosphere. In the Lanxide process, since the infiltration process requires a relatively long time at around 800 C to complete, alloys containing about 8-10 wt% silicon are needed in the manufacture of SiC/Al composites to retard detrimental interfacial reactions. Although the process has been successful in producing composites of intricate shapes without vacuum or external pressures, the processing time is in terms of hours and the process can be used only with relatively stable thermodynamic/kinetic systems. In other words, using the Lanxide process, neither can SiC reinforcements be incorporated into low silicon content aluminum alloys nor can carbon fibers be incorporated into aluminum alloys without a protective coating.

Over the last few years, a pressureless liquid infiltration process using infrared heating, rapid infrared manufacturing (RIM), has been developed at the University of Cincinnati for fabricating ceramic fiber reinforced metal matrix composites [10-25]. Both aluminum and titanium matrix composites reinforced with carbon and SiC fibers have been successfully prepared by a pressureless infrared infiltration technique. The fast heating and cooling rates and precise temperature control produces aluminum and titanium matrix composites in a very short time (1-2 minutes) without the aid of any external pressure or vacuum. Aluminum and titanium matrix composites made with this process show no noticeable fiber degradation. Compare to processes mentioned above, the infrared pressureless infiltration is a low cost process with the capability of producing high quality composites. The infrared processed titanium matrix composites reinforced with SCS-6 fibers show strengths and moduli as high as 1734 MPa and 195 GPa, respectively. For carbon fiber reinforced titanium matrix composites, the strength and modulus are as high as 1100 MPa and 200 GPa, respectively. Aluminum matrix composites with carbon, SCS-2 and Nicalon fibers have also been prepared with infrared infiltration. The high strength and modulus in the composites fabricated by this technique is believed to be a direct result of small and well controlled interfacial reaction. In this study, we report results on infrared fabricated aluminum matrix composites with carbon, Nicalon or SCS-2 fiber reinforcement. Interfacial reactions occurred during processing for each system will be discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

The infrared infiltration process consists of heating the fibers and the alloy in a graphite crucible under an ambient inert gas atmosphere to temperatures above 1000 C. Our previous studies have shown that at temperatures above 1000 C, the wetting and flow characteristics of the Al alloy become favorable for pressureless infiltration. The liquid alloy is held in contact with the fibers for times ranging from 5-30 seconds. The sample is then quickly cooled to temperatures below the solidus of the alloy. The selective infrared absorption characteristics of different materials prevent the furnace walls from being heated and facilitate heating rates in the order of 100-200 C/seconds. The fast ramping capability of the process restricts the oxidation of the aluminum alloy and aids in improved wetting and flow characteristics. The fibers used were P-55 carbon fibers from Union

Carbide, Nicalon SiC fibers from Dow Corning, and SCS-2 fibers from Textron Specialty Materials of Lowell, MA. The matrix was the 6061 aluminum alloy. Composites made were 25 x 6.2 x 1.5 mm in size with 10-12 vol% fibers. To release interfacial stresses, six SCS-2 reinforced composites were solutionized and aged as per the T6 procedure[24]. Some SCS-2 reinforced composites were further subjected to an additional thermal treatment, the details of which are not disclosed in this study for proprietary reasons. The modified heat treatment is designated as T6-M. All samples were polished to a 600 grit finish and subjected to three point flexural testing using an Instron testing machine equipped with a data acquisition system. The testing was done in accordance with the ASTM specification D-790-86[25]. A span to depth, L/d ratio of 12 was maintained. The load was applied perpendicular to the fibers causing tensile stresses to develop on the outer surface of the composite in a direction parallel to the fiber axis. For microstructural examinations, composites were cut perpendicular to the fiber direction, mounted and polished down to 0.25 μm using diamond pastes. The samples were first examined under an optical microscope with image analysis capability, then, coated with gold and viewed under a scanning electron microscope (SEM) with energy dispersive x-ray (EDX) analysis.

RESULTS

Typically, aluminum composites made with infrared show excellent infiltration. Very few voids were observed from the cross section microstructure examination. Figure 1 shows several SEM photos of the composites made with infrared. Various degree of the interfacial reaction was detected depending on the types of reinforcement fibers, processing temperature and time.

Figure 1. Micrographs for aluminum matrix composites with (a) SCS-2 fiber reinforcements, (b) carbon fiber, and (c) Nicalon fiber.

Mechanical properties measured from the bend test are reported in Table 1. The strength values for carbon fiber/Al and Nicalon fiber/Al composites was low due to poor fiber alignment. No systematic measurements for these composites were done.

Table 1. Flexural strengths of as-processed and heat treated Al matrix composites.

Material	Strength (MPa)
SCS-2/Al (as-processed) 12 fiber vol%	522
SCS-2/Al (T6) 12 fiber vol%	551
SCS-2/Al (T6-M) 12 fiber vol%	722

DISCUSSION

Aluminum forms compounds with both carbon and silicon carbide. Figure 2 shows the reaction products formed in carbon fiber reinforced aluminum composites after liquid fabrication. From TEM examination, the structure of aluminum carbide has been identified in both SiC/Al and C/Al composites (Fig. 3).

Figure 2. Electron microprobe analysis of reaction interfaces in aluminum matrix composites.

Figure 3. TEM micrographs of interfacial reaction products.

On top of forming the reaction product on the fiber surface, depending on the chemistry of the matrix, precipitates can be formed in the matrix. This may occur either during heating or along with solidification of matrix upon cooling. During heating, the formation of these precipitates may occur when the extend of fiber dissolution exceeds the solubility limit of certain precipitates in the matrix. For example, in the SiC/Al composite system, during liquid processing, SiC dissolves in molten aluminum to form atomic Si and C. As dissolution proceeds, the concentrations of Si and C would increase to a point that Al_4C_3 may start to form. The maximum concentration of carbon in aluminum before Al_4C_3 formation may be determined from the thermochemical data of the system. Since Al-Si is a simple eutectic binary system, no Al-Si intermetallic compound will precipitate. Thus, the only possible precipitate in the SiC/Al composite is Al_4C_3 . Similar Al_4C_3 precipitates have been observed in the C/Al composite system. However, in this case, in stead of forming precipitate in the matrix, a reaction product layer of Al_4C_3 will grow on the fiber surface.

THERMODYNAMIC CONSIDERATIONS

The Gibbs standard free energies of a few reactions in the aluminum matrix composite systems are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Free energy data for carbides existed in aluminum matrix composites.

No.	Reaction	ΔG°_f , kJ/mol	Temperature, K
(1)	$\text{Si(l)} + \text{C(gr)} = \text{SiC(s)}$	$-123,470 + 37.6 T$	1000-2000
(2)	$4\text{Al(l)} + 3\text{C(gr)} = \text{Al}_4\text{C}_3\text{(s)}$	$-266,520 + 96.2 T$	932-2000
(3)	$3\text{SiC(s)} + 4\text{Al(l)} = \text{Al}_4\text{C}_3\text{(s)} + 3\text{Si(l)}$	$103,900 - 16.5 T$	1000-2000

At 1100 C, the processing temperature used in this study, and in the presence of molten aluminum, the standard free energy of Reaction (3) is 81,245J, suggesting that the tendency of forming Al_4C_3 is not strong unless the activity of Si in molten aluminum is low. Using the thermochemical data from the Al-Si binary system compiled by Hultgren et al. [27], it can be obtained that, in the presence of both SiC(s) and $\text{Al}_4\text{C}_3\text{(s)}$, the aluminum melt may contain up to about 15 wt% Si at 1100 C, with the Al activity being 0.78. The corresponding carbon activity with graphite as the standard state is 0.003. Since the solubility of carbon in molten aluminum is 0.16 wt% at 1100 C, the activity of carbon in Al(l) may be expressed as

$$a_c = 6.25 \times (\text{wt\% C}) \quad (4)$$

The concentration of carbon in equilibrium with both SiC(s) and $\text{Al}_4\text{C}_3\text{(s)}$ is, therefore, 0.00048 wt%. This calculation result indicates that SiC will continue to dissolve in molten Al and Al_4C_3 will form to keep the carbon concentration to be at 0.00048 wt% until the Si concentration has accumulated to the equilibrium level of 15 wt%. To prevent the formation of Al_4C_3 , the Si concentration (activity) will have to be greater than 15 wt%. This can be achieved with Si addition in the matrix or by the presence of free silicon on the surface of SiC .

KINETICS OF INTERFACIAL REACTIONS

SCS-2 Fiber/Aluminum Composites

SEM images of the fiber-matrix interface in as-processed and heat treated composites, Figure 4, show that the interface region consists of SiC , unreacted pyrocarbon coating, a layer of reaction product, and finally, aluminum. X-ray elemental mapping indicated that there were minor

Figure 4. SEM cross sections of SCS-2/Al composites (a) as fabricated, (b) T6 treated, and (c) T6-M treated.

amounts of aluminum diffusion into the coating and no significant silicon diffusion into the matrix. There was no significant difference in the thickness of the reaction zone in as-processed and heat treated composites.

Carbon Fiber/Al Composites

In these composites, aluminum carbide growth occurred with a plate like morphology with the platelets originating from the fiber surface. Since the activities of both carbon and aluminum are essentially unity and the free energy of carbide formation is highly negative, Al_4C_3 crystals should nucleate rather uniformly over the entire fiber surface. On an atomic level, in graphitized fibers such as the P-55 fibers, a large amount of basal planes lie parallel to the fiber circumference [28]. Although the basal planes are relatively inert, nucleation may occur preferentially along the high energy basal edges [29]. Al_4C_3 showed faceted growth characteristics with growth occurring in a direction parallel to the carbide basal planes. The orientation relationship between Al_4C_3 platelets and graphitic planes has been observed by Diwanji and Hall[30]. They have found that about 10-15 % of Al_4C_3 platelets followed an orientation relationship of

which means that Al_4C_3 basal planes lie parallel to the graphite basal planes. Since in graphite fibers, a large amount of basal planes lie parallel to the fiber circumference [28], due to the preferred growth direction observed in Al_4C_3 crystals, it is likely that a significant amount of nuclei would start to grow nearly tangential to the fiber surface, quickly impinge upon each other and cease to grow any further for those being blocked. On the other hand, nuclei that do not impinge upon each other can continue to grow with a plate like morphology as a result of free energy minimization based on surface energy considerations.

Figure 5. Platelike carbide morphology in as processed aluminum matrix composites.

Nicalon Fiber/Al Composites

Kannikeswaran and Lin [31] studied the thermodynamics of reactions in the SiC/Al system. They proposed a stability domain diagram of various phases as a function of carbon and silicon activities in the melt. According to their calculations SiC exists in equilibrium with dissolved silicon only at silicon concentrations greater than 10 wt% (assuming ideal behavior) at 1100 C.

The 6061 alloy contains only small amounts of silicon (0.4 to 0.8 wt%) [32]. Also, the amount of silicon from the dissolved fibers is extremely small and not detectable by microprobe analysis. Therefore, during processing, since only small amounts of Si is present in the alloy, only Al_4C_3 formation is feasible. In other words, during fabrication, when the molten alloy comes in contact with SiC fibers, SiC would dissolve in the alloy until the concentration of carbon in the alloy reaches that in equilibrium with Al_4C_3 and liquid aluminum. Further dissolution occurs along with both SiC and Al_4C_3 formation.

Nicalon SiC fibers are not stoichiometric and contain significant amounts of free carbon and SiO_2 [33-35]. Typically, the weight percentages of SiC, C and SiO_2 are 61, 10 and 28, respectively. Al_4C_3 formed from free carbon would act as nucleation sites for Al_4C_3 growth from the saturated solution. Although carbon particles have been qualitatively reported to be uniformly distributed within the fiber[35], the size distribution and shape of these particles are not uniform as deduced from high resolution micrographs from work by Yajima et al.[34] Consequently, the nucleation and growth of Al_4C_3 are not even. Thus, non-uniform and discontinuous precipitation of Al_4C_3 occurs along the circumference of the fibers. As dissolution proceeds, since more carbon particles are being exposed from within the fibers, Al_4C_3 growth continues to occur in between the previously formed precipitates. It is likely that these discontinuous precipitates may coalesce. Thus, in the initial stages of dissolution, globules of Al_4C_3 may form. With a long processing time, since Al_4C_3 has a tendency for growth along preferred directions, the majority of Al_4C_3 formed has a plate like appearance. TEM images showed Al_4C_3 platelets originating out of the fiber surface. As stated in the previous section, it is possible that some favorably oriented Al_4C_3 nuclei which form from carbon particles can grow outwards in the form of platelets. Different growth mechanisms in the SiC/Al system were also observed by Handwerker et al.[36] They noted that during thermal exposure at 920 C, Al_4C_3 appeared to grow as either discontinuous isolated precipitates on the (0001)SiC plane or as a continuous layer on other planes.

CONCLUSIONS

Results from this study indicate that even with seconds of processing time, liquid infiltration of aluminum matrix composites would have significant amount of interfacial reaction. For both carbon fiber and Nicalon fiber reinforcements, aluminum carbide was detected on the fiber surface after infiltration. To prepare composites with proper interfaces and, thus, reproducible mechanical properties, the processing time for aluminum matrix composites during any liquid state process must be remain short, in the order of seconds. It appears that due to rapid heating and cooling, infrared processing is able to generate composite with has the advantages of short processing time and, thus, produce little interfacial zone.

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